

PRODIGEES

*Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe
Towards Sustainable Development*

How to use this flow chart: Please use this document as a guide and reference for completing all obligations as a seconded PRODIGEES researcher. Carefully read the entire document before you begin work with PRODIGEES. If you have questions, please contact the PRODIGEES Project Manager (Benjamin Stewart: benjamin.stewart@idos-research.de).

Researcher Flow Chart

Before

<input type="checkbox"/>	I have contacted my Host Institution 3-6 months in advance , and I have inquired about the public health situation , the current regulations and the logistics of my secondment.
<input type="checkbox"/>	I have a general schedule stating where I am going, when I am going, and how long I need to be there.
<input type="checkbox"/>	I have an explanation of my budget , which I can acquire from my Originating Institution
<input type="checkbox"/>	I have a specific agenda with my project details and the relevant research timeline. I must create this agenda and forward it to the PRODIGEES Project Manager and to the contact at my Host Institution. This is a 1-2 page proposal for your research topic, methodology, goals, and timeline.
<input type="checkbox"/>	I have a passport , the proper visa in order to enter the host country legally, and individual insurance .
<input type="checkbox"/>	I have the required vaccinations, medical examinations, and necessary medication for the country and the duration of travel. For information, consult the Center for Disease Control and Prevention website: https://wwwnc.cdc.gov/travel/
<input type="checkbox"/>	I arranged housing in the host country. (You can contact the Host Institution for housing advice and assistance.)
<input type="checkbox"/>	I am maintaining proof of my travel and living expenses (i.e. flight tickets, rental contracts, etc.) for the Secondment Activity Report and for providing to the PRODIGEES Project Manager upon request.
<input type="checkbox"/>	I received a signed Letter of Invitation from the Host Institute, and I forwarded the Letter of Invitation to the PRODIGEES Project Manager.
<input type="checkbox"/>	I read the PRODIGEES Data Protection Policy (found on Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/communities/prodigees/), briefing me on the General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR).
<input type="checkbox"/>	I downloaded, read and signed the Researcher Declaration (found on Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/communities/prodigees/), which allows me to be registered with PRODIGEES on the EU's online portal. I forwarded the signed Researcher Declaration to the PRODIGEES Project Manager.
<input type="checkbox"/>	I confirmed with my employer and/or any third-party sponsor that their funding scheme is compatible with this EU Horizon 2020 MSCA-RISE action.
<input type="checkbox"/>	I read and signed the Researcher Commitment (found on Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/communities/prodigees/), in which I confirm my understanding and commitment to the PRODIGEES ethics guidelines. I forwarded the signed Researcher Commitment to the PRODIGEES Project Manager.

During

<input type="checkbox"/>	I received a signed Secondment Arrival Letter from the Host Institution. (Just in case the Host Institution does not have this letter prepared for you, download and adapt the Secondment Arrival Letter template from Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/prodigees/), and present it to your Host Institution for signature upon your arrival.)
<input type="checkbox"/>	I downloaded and began filling out the Secondment Activity Report (found on Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/communities/prodigees/), which details activities, expenses, meetings, publications, and other items relevant to the secondment. (Please use this template as a guide for writing and submitting your mandatory secondment report. We recommend updating this report regularly <i>during</i> your secondment in order to not miss important details.)
<input type="checkbox"/>	If needed, I downloaded and adapted the Informed Consent Form (found on Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/communities/prodigees/), in which I require a research subject’s signature to participate in the research. (This document is a template which will need to be adapted with information from your specific research project.)
<input type="checkbox"/>	If needed, I downloaded and adapted the Informed Consent Information Sheet (found on Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/communities/prodigees/), which describes to the research subject the obligations of the Institution to uphold the GDPR and ethics guidelines. (This document is also a template which will need to be adapted with information from your specific research project.)
<input type="checkbox"/>	If needed, I downloaded the Data Consent Form (found on Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/communities/prodigees/), which research subjects must sign so that I may legally process their personal data.
<input type="checkbox"/>	I kept receipts and records of my expenses and my working hours (e.g. timesheets) in case of audit by the Coordinator or the EU.
<input type="checkbox"/>	I presented at 1 Lecture/Seminar/Workshop* at my Host Institution, facilitating an academic discussion and a transnational knowledge exchange between professionals, researchers, staff, and the interested public.

***Important:** The EU funding statement and logo (seen in the footer below) must appear on all publications and presentation materials associated with PRODIGEES.

After

<input type="checkbox"/>	<p>I submitted my Secondment Activity Report to the PRODIGEES Project Manager within 30 days of the end of the secondment.</p>
<input type="checkbox"/>	<p>I wrote an Article for a Newsletter, including a picture, in which I summarized my research, noted my conclusions, and reflected upon the outcomes and the future of the research. This is an article between 250 and 1000 words, to be written for the newsletter of the Originating Institute or a comparable newsletter channel. Then the link to this newsletter article is to be sent to the PRODIGEES Project Manager within 30 days of its publication.</p>
<input type="checkbox"/>	<p>I produced a Written Publication/Publishable Work, which can be a journal article, book, book chapter, edited volume, policy brief, working paper, concept paper, or similar <i>draft</i> of all or part of the work. In the event that publishable work is foreseen to need more than 30 days past the end of the secondment for completion, please contact the PRODIGEES Project Manager to establish a timeline for submission. The publication must remain open access. What is open access? Here's a link: https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/goals-research-and-innovation-policy/open-science/open-access_en</p>
<input type="checkbox"/>	<p>I produced a Digital Knowledge Product, which can be a video, podcast, infographic, data visualization, animation strip, virtual study element, or other e-learning content, based upon the results of my research. The idea of the Digital Knowledge Product is to provide a dynamic, easy-to-understand version of your research results for the public. Please submit your Digital Knowledge Product to the PRODIGEES Project Manager within 30 days after the end of your secondment.</p>
<input type="checkbox"/>	<p>I presented at 1 Lecture/Seminar/Workshop at my Originating Institution, facilitating an academic discussion and a transnational knowledge exchange between professionals, researchers, staff, and the interested public.</p>
<input type="checkbox"/>	<p>I wrote a Future Action Plan, which describes follow-up research based upon my project results. This is a 1-2 page proposal which outlines future projects and implications for your research on your specific topic. Please send the Future Action Plan to the PRODIGEES Project Manager within 30 days after the end of your secondment.</p>
<input type="checkbox"/>	<p>I filled out the questionnaire from the EU's MSCA-RISE program. I am aware that in two years I will be required to fill out another questionnaire from MSCA-RISE.</p>

